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SEMANTIC FEATURES OF THE CONCEPT OF “LOVE-MUHABBAT” IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

As is known, love is one of the concepts related to the emotional state and inner experiences of a person's life. Regardless of a person's place of residence, nationality, religious position and origin, this concept means expressing a person's experiences arising from their relationship to real things and events, people and themselves. This article aims to study the semantic characteristics of the concept of “love-muhabbat” in English and Uzbek by analyzing its linguistic expressions, cultural changes, etymological origins and psychological foundations. Through a comprehensive review of the existing literature and a qualitative analysis of language use, this study explores and discusses the concepts of how the concept of “love-muhabbat” is verbally, conceptualized, semantic space, and how it is expressed in different contexts in English and Uzbek.

Key words: linguistics, semantic features, concept, love, comparative, etymologic analyses, lexical analyses, Lexical combinations, Cultural connotations sevgi, muhabbat, ishq.

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INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA “LOVE-MUHABBAT” KONSEPTINING SEMANTIK XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ma'lumki, muhabbat shaxs hayotining hissiy holati, ichki kechinmalari bilan bog'liq bo'lgan tushunchalardan biri hisoblanadi. Insonning yashash joyi, millati dini mavqeyi va kelib chiqishidan qat'iy nazar, bu tushuncha shaxsning voqelikdagi narsa va hodisalarga, kishilarga hamda o'z-o'ziga bo'lgan munosabatlardan kelib chiqadigan kechinmalarini ifodalashni anglatadi. Ushbu maqola ingliz va o'zbek tillarida “love-muhabbat” konseptining lingvistik ifodalari, madaniy o'zgarishlari, etimologik kelib chiqishi va psixologik asoslarini tahlil qilish orqali uning semantik xususiyatlarini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Mavjud adabiyotlarni har tomonlama ko'rib chiqish va tildan foydalanishni sifatli tahlil qilish orqali ushbu tadqiqot “love-muhabbat” konseptini qanday og'zaki, kontseptuallashtirilganligi, semantik maydoni, turli kontekstlarda qanday ifodalanishi haqida tushunchalarni o'rganadi va muhokama qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: tilshunoslik, semantik xususiyatlar, konsept, love, qiyosiy tahlil, etimologik tahlil, lug'aviy tahlil, leksik birikmalar, madaniy konnotatsiyalar, sevgi, muhabbat, ishq.

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СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ КОНЦЕПТ «LOVE-MUHABBAT» В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Как известно, любовь является одним из понятий, связанных с эмоциональным состоянием и внутренними переживаниями жизни человека. Независимо от места проживания человека, национальности, религиозной позиции и происхождения, это понятие означает выражение переживаний человека, возникающих из его отношения к реальным вещам и событиям, людям и самому себе. Целью данной статьи является изучение семантических характеристик понятия «love-muhabbat» в английском и узбекском языках путем анализа его языковых выражений, культурных изменений, этимологического происхождения и психологических основ. Посредством всестороннего обзора существующей литературы и качественного анализа использования языка данное исследование исследует и обсуждает концепции того, как понятие «love-muhabbat» вербально, концептуализировано, семантическое пространство и как оно выражается в различных контекстах в английском и узбекском языках.

Ключевые слова: лингвистика, семантические признаки, концепт, любовь, сравнительный, этимологический анализы, лексический анализы, лексические сочетания, культурные коннотации sevgi, muhabbat, ishq.

INTRODUCTION

Love is one of the most universal emotions known to humanity. Love is a deep and multifaceted emotion, encompassing a wide range of meanings, from romantic desire to family bonds, spiritual devotion, and altruism. The lexeme of love occupies a central place in human relationships and cultures, shaping the way people and societies relate to each other. However, despite its universality, the concept of love has developed differently in different languages and cultural contexts.

Love is a complex and multifaceted emotion that transcends cultural, linguistic, and temporal boundaries. Despite its ubiquity, the semantic features of love are highly variable, influenced by cultural norms, linguistic structures, and individual experiences. This study seeks to unravel the intricate semantic features associated with the concept of love, providing insights into how it is perceived and expressed.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative approach, analyzing textual data from literature, interviews, and surveys. The data is coded and categorized based on themes and patterns to identify the semantic features of love. Additionally, cross-cultural comparisons are made to highlight variations in the conceptualization and expression of love.

The concept of love has been explored extensively in various academic fields. From the psychological perspective, love is often categorized into different types such as romantic love, platonic love, and familial love. Sociologists have examined the role of love in forming social bonds and its impact on social structures. Linguists have studied the language of love, investigating how different cultures verbalize and conceptualize this emotion.

In recent years, research has been conducted in various directions in modern linguistics on the concept of love. In particular, the direction of those who seek love as an integral part of the national mentality. According to the scientist V.V. Kolesov, who conducted research in this direction, “love” is the dominant of Russian culture, it is a separate linguistic and cultural value. Another group of

scientists studies the concept of love as a metalinguistic concept. An example of this is A. Verzbitskaya. They try to identify aspects of an adequate interpretation of the concept of love related to metalinguistics. Also, another direction is linguists who study the concept of love as a linguocultural concept. One of the representatives of this direction is S.G. Vorkachev. They describe the ethnosemantics of the concepts of “Love” and “Happiness” in Russian and English, reflecting the uniqueness of the concept of love in their research. Linguist L.E. Kuznetsova, on the other hand, studies the concept of love from an ethical and psychological perspective, develops a semantic model of the concept of love, and lays the foundation for the direction of those who study the concept of love as an irrational feeling, that is, through the semantic model of love.

In English linguistics, several English scholars have explored the various aspects of the concept of “Love” from different perspectives. An example is the “Conceptual Metaphor Theory” (CMT) by George Lakoff and Mark Johnson. This theory argues that love is a product of human thought. Zick Rubin, known for his work on measuring romantic love, emphasizes the importance of attachment and emotional connection. Another English linguist, Stephen Johnson, in his book “The Feeling of Love: The Revolutionary New Science of Romantic Relationships,” explores the neurobiology of love and its impact on relationships. M.D.S. Ainsworth also conducted research on infant attachment and the development of love relationships, and his research has had a significant impact on understanding the psychological foundations of love.

RESULTS

This article studies the semantic features of the concepts of “love” and “muhabbat” in English and Uzbek using comparative, etymological and lexical analysis. As a result of studying the texts of literary works, explanatory and etymological dictionaries in both languages, as well as the research of linguists, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The main meaning of the concept of “love-muhabbat” in the semantic field:

In English, the term “love” mainly includes a wide semantic field, such as romantic affection between a young man and a girl, family care, friendship and passion for activities or things. These lexemes can form a wide range of semantic meanings depending on the context.

In Uzbek, “muhabbat” primarily means devoted love for family and spouse. In Uzbek, the concept of love is used synonymously with lexemes such as “sevgi”, “ishq”.

2. Cultural connotations:

- English concepts of love often emphasize individualism and personal choice, reflecting Western cultural values. For example, expressions such as “to fall in love” and “to love at first sight” emphasize spontaneous and personal feelings.

- In Uzbek culture, “muhabbat” embodies a sense of duty and respect that reflects collective values. The expression “muhabbat” is often associated with family expectations and social norms.

3. Lexical combinations:

In English, the concept of “love” is often combined with lexemes such as “true,” “eternal,” “unconditional,” and “crazy.” In Uzbek, the concept of “muhabbat” is often combined with words such as “sodiqlik,” “ishonch,” and “mehr.”

4. Gender and social roles:

The English concept of love often portrays both sexes as equal participants in expressing and pursuing love. In the Uzbek national mentality, “muhabbat” often portrays men as the initiator, with women playing a secondary role in expressing love.

DISCUSSION

The findings reveal significant differences in how “love” and “muhabbat” are conceptualized in English and Uzbek, shaped by their respective linguistic and cultural contexts. These differences underscore the importance of understanding the interplay between language and culture in expressing universal human emotions.

1. The first use of the concept of “love”

Although the theme of love has been a familiar topic for Western philosophy and theology for a very long time, the lexeme “love” that participates in its nomination is a word that was added to the English lexicon later. The occurrence of the lexeme “Love” in written sources dates back to the 1100s,

and this lexeme comes from the root of the noun form “Lubo” and the verb form “lubojanan”, which belong to the Germanic group of the Indo-European language family (proto-Germanic), and meant the semes love, like, affection.

The first use of the concept of “muhabbat”

In the Uzbek language, the concept of “muhabbat” can be found in the works of writers, poets, and thinkers for a long time. Thinkers who lived and worked in Central Asia have long paid great attention to the issue of love. They understood love between people, including love between a man and a woman, as a high relationship. As an example, it is known that Abu Ali Ibn Sina wrote a special scientific work about love. In the opinion of Yusuf Khos Hajib, love is the basis for a strong family life and social improvement. According to Lutfi, love is closely related to esteem, loyalty, and devotion. Alisher Navoi divides love into 3 semantic groups: sexual relations that take place in marriage between a man and a woman, love that manifests itself in relationships between people in general, and love for God.

2. Etymology:

If we consider the etymological origin of the concept of “love” (n), the Old English word *lufu* (affection; romantic sexual attraction; affection; friendship; love of God; abstract or figurative love) is found in the form of the Proto-Germanic *lubo* (from the Old High Germanic source *liubi*, meaning “joy”, German *Liebe* “love” in Old Norse, Old Frisian and Dutch *lof*; German *Lob* “praise”; Old Saxon *liofi*, Old Frisian *liaf*, Dutch *liaf*, Old High German *liob*, German *lieb*, Gothic *liufs* “valuable, beloved”). The words of the Germanic languages, which belong to this Proto-Indo-European language family, come from the root *leubh-* “care, desire, love”.

If we pay attention to the etymology of the concept of love in the Uzbek language, Volume 1 of the Etymological Dictionary of the Uzbek Language, edited by Shavkat Rahmatullayev, lists the forms of the word love as *sevmoq*, *muhabbat bog‘lamoq*, *yaxshi ko‘rmoq*, *yoqtirmoq*. For example, *U meni tug‘ishgan opamdan afzal sevadi* (Oybek). This lexeme, which also reflects this meaning in the ancient Turkic language, was pronounced as *säbmoq*, *sävmoq*, *sebmoq*, *sövmoq*, *sevmoq*. It is clear from this that initially this verb had vowels *ä/ë*, which over time were replaced by the vowel *e*: *säbmoq*, *sövmoq*, *sebmoq*, *sevmoq*. This verb is also used in oral speech as *suymoq*, meaning to like.

3. Semantik maydoni va xususiyatlari

We analyzed the semantic field of the concept of “Love” in English dictionaries. In the Longman Dictionary of Modern English, edited by Della Summers, published in 2005, the lexical unit “Love” includes the following meanings: to be romantically attracted, to care for, to like, to show loyalty, to enjoy, to enjoy, while in the Macmillan Dictionary of English, edited by Michael Rundell, it includes the following meanings: to have an emotional and sexual attraction towards someone, to care for family members, close friends, to enjoy. The Merriam-Webster Dictionary, newly published in 2016, describes the lexeme “love” as having the following semantic variants: strong affection, warm feelings toward a person, thing, or place, sexual attraction, a beloved person, someone who is fair and loyal to others, and a gentle and affectionate touch or kiss.

In contrast, in the Uzbek language, we can see that the lexemes “muhabbat, sevgi, ishq” are embodied in the core of the main meaning, and are directed towards family relationships, affection and loyalty to one's spouse, or more precisely, love between spouses and love for God.

As we continue our discussion, let's look at the linguistic expressions of Love. Metaphors and Similes: Love is often described using metaphors and similes, such as “love is a journey” or “love is a fire.” These linguistic devices vividly describe the emotion and its effects. Also, Adjectives and Intensifiers: The use of adjectives (e.g., passionate, eternal) and intensifiers (e.g., deep, true) emphasize the intensity and quality of love.

Considering that the concept of love is a cultural concept, Cultural Variations are as follows:

Western Cultures: Love in Western cultures is often romanticized, with a strong emphasis on individualism and privacy. It is linked to sexual desire and attraction, and passion plays a major role. Looking at Eastern cultures, in contrast, it may reflect broader cultural values, emphasizing familial love, marital commitment, trust between couples, and the community-oriented aspects of love.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, while the fundamental essence of “love-muhabbat” remains a deeply human experience shared across cultures, its semantic features are shaped by linguistic, cultural, and social contexts. Understanding these nuances enriches our appreciation of how love is perceived and experienced differently around the world, fostering greater empathy and cross-cultural understanding. The concept of “love” is among the cultural concepts and is embodied in a semantic field that is inextricably linked to such concepts as happiness, joy, friendship, loyalty, trust. Love is a universal concept, and is understood and interpreted differently in different peoples, based on their culture and values. One of the concepts that expresses human emotions in English is the lexical unit “love”. The existence of the concept of “love” in any language, despite being expressed as a universal concept, reflects certain semantic features in each language, based on the culture, traditions and values of the peoples. The semantic features of the concept of love are deeply embedded in linguistic expressions, cultural norms and psychological foundations. This study highlights the rich and diverse ways of conceptualizing and verbalizing love, and offers a comprehensive understanding of this universal, but deeply personal feeling.

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